

DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF UZBEK POP ART
IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: the role of vocal and pop performance in the modern musical culture of the world and the Republic of Uzbekistan is very large and has a long history of development. This article talks about many issues and stages of historical development related to the development of vocal and pop performance in the culture of modern Uzbekistan. Studying the development of vocal and pop performance in the modern culture of Uzbekistan, it would be appropriate to first look at the history of its development. Since nothing appeared on its own, of course, in its appearance, such innovations and “discoveries” appear due to certain requests and needs.

Keywords: music, art, stage, history, performance, voice, singer, teacher, soloist.

Uzbekistan has a long and rich music, dance, and theatre history. Traditional music is a mix of local rhythms, melodies, and influences from neighboring countries, such as Kazakhstan and Tajikistan. Traditional instruments include the dutar (long-necked lute) and the doira (a kind of drum). Traditional dances are usually performed to celebrate weddings and other special occasions.

Uzbekistan also has a vibrant film industry, with the country producing some of the most popular films in the region. Directors such as Bakhrom Yakubov and Timur Bekmambetov have made a name for themselves with their cinematic works, focusing on identity and self-discovery themes.

Uzbekistan has a vibrant and diverse music scene, with many genres represented. Popular music genres include hip-hop, rap, rock, and electronica.

Famous Uzbekistani musicians include Shoxrux Mirzo, Timur Murodov, and Jahongir Otamuradov.

Pop culture in Uzbekistan is an ever-evolving mix of traditional and modern influences. It reflects the country's diverse population and culture and is a great way to experience the country and its people. Pop culture in Uzbekistan has a long and rich history, dating back to the days of the Silk Road. From trade and commerce came various cultural influences, including music, Art, and fashion. This influence has been kept alive today and can be seen in the country's vibrant music, Art, and style.

In our republic, a number of important measures are being taken to promote pop music. For example, on the initiative of the head of the "Zamin STV" studio, S. Abdullaev, the remarkable show-festival "Zamin Stars" has been held since 1998. This festival, which aims to support the masters of art and sports of our republic, is gaining the same prestige as the "Oscar", "Nika", "Golden Globe", "Golden Oven", "Golden Bear" festivals held worldwide. Since 2000, the festival has achieved the status of "International Festival". Famous art and sports stars from foreign countries were also invited to "Zamin Stars" this year, and they were among the winners of the "Zamin Stars" award. Among them are the star of Turkish cinema, Aydan Shaner, the main character of the movie "Choliqushi", and Gunel, a young pop star from Azerbaijan. Also, a number of pop art representatives, in particular famous singers such as Farrukh Zoyirov, Nasiba Abdullaeva, Rustam Goyipov, Muhridin Holikov, Nuriddin Haydarov, Kumush Razzokova, Yulduz Abdullaeva, and the "Setora" group also received the "Zamin Stars" award. In the future, it is planned to further expand the scope of the "Zamin Yuduzli" festival. It should be noted that currently Uzbek pop music is experiencing a complex process in terms of its style. In particular, we can see the influence of melodies and rhythms from Middle Eastern folk music to Latin and North American and Western European popular music. Free use of popular music styles (from disco and hard rock to rap and heavy metal) that were banned or not

"supported" by the state in the previous period, and experiments in bringing samples of national traditional music to the pop scene. 1991 began to occupy a wide place from the year. At the same time, new currents of musical variety are developing in Uzbekistan, including such directions and styles as "techno-pop", "punk", "hard-rock", "reggae" and "jazz-rock", "bard" singing among young people. "Kars" ("Chiprodalli-dalli", "Yor-yor, yoroney"), which matured under the leadership of Sarvar Qaziev and rose to the level of prize-winners of various pop contests, as well as "Tashkent" ("Quilt") and "Manzur" ("You can't, "Meni Yor Dema") groups, Muhammadjon Ro'zimammedov and "Shofayz", Daniyori Mamedov and "Bayram", Abdulla Shomag'rupov and "Nola" ("Feeling", "Sensan Sevarim"), Rashid Khalikov and "Shahzod" ("Oynaysan", "Kelinchak"), Sevara Nazarkhan and "Sideriz" ("Don't forget"), Abdulaziz Karim and "Asr" ("I will be a victim"), Tahir Sadikov and "Bolalar", "Khoja", "Taj", "Sahar" the present era is the selected segment of youth pop music. Talented singers who rose to the level of Uzbek pop stars in 1991-2001 - Yulduz Usmanova, Gulomjon Yakubov, Kumush Razzokova, Kozim Qamov, Azim Mullakhanov, Ravshan Nomozov, and Alisher Ikramov, Dilorom Omonullaeva, Alisher Rasulov, Vladimir Baramikov of the "Kars" and "Tashkent" groups. , Sarg Qaziev, created in close cooperation with composers and arrangers, and made a great contribution to the development of pop music

In the music of Uzbekistan, traditional instruments such as the dutar, surnay, and rubab are still used and often combined with modern appliances like the piano, guitar, and drums. This combination of traditional and contemporary tools creates a unique and exciting sound. Music in Uzbekistan is often full of energy and can be heard at festivals, weddings, and other public events.

Art in Uzbekistan is also heavily influenced by traditional culture. Painters, sculptors, and other artists often draw from the country's rich history, creating Art that captures the beauty and spirit of the country. There is also a strong interest in

modern Art, as Uzbekistan has many contemporary artists pushing the boundaries of what is possible in Art.

Uzbek fashion is also heavily influenced by traditional culture. Women wear brightly colored dresses and shawls, while men wear traditional robes and hats. These garments often feature intricate embroidery and other details that reflect the country's cultural heritage. In recent years, there has been a resurgence of interest in traditional Uzbek fashion, with many designers creating modern interpretations of classic garments. Pop culture in Uzbekistan is alive and well and continues to evolve with the times. From traditional music, Art, and fashion to modern interpretations of these elements, Uzbekistan has a unique and vibrant culture that will captivate visitors and locals alike.

Fashion is a significant reflection of pop culture in Uzbekistan. The country's young people are heavily influenced by international trends, particularly those from the United States, Europe, and South Korea. From clothing and makeup to hairstyles, these trends have become popular among youth and shape how they present themselves to the world. Music is another area where pop culture has significantly impacted Uzbekistan. International artists and genres have become famous throughout the country, and local musicians often incorporate elements of these styles into their music. This has led to a new music scene in the country, with many bands and singers blending traditional Uzbek music with modern pop influences.

Pop culture also affects how people think and interact, particularly regarding social values and political discourse. With more people exposed to international trends and ideas, there is a greater acceptance of diversity and progressive values. This has led to more open and tolerant attitudes towards different genders, sexualities, and ethnicities in Uzbekistan. Pop culture has influenced the country's economic policies, as international companies often use popular cultural trends to market their products. This has led to increased consumerism and the growth of specific industries, such as fashion and entertainment.

Music and dance are two of the most famous art forms in the world. They have been around for centuries and have been used to express emotions, tell stories, and bring people together. Music and dance are also great forms of physical activity that can improve your physical and mental health. Music is the Art of creating sounds with the combination of instruments, voices, and other sounds. It can range from classical music to pop music and everything in between. Music can be used to create a mood or atmosphere, to tell a story, or just to let people express themselves.

Dance is the Art of moving your body in time with the music. It can range from traditional dance forms such as ballet and tap to modern-day forms such as hip-hop and street dance. Dance is a great way to express emotions, tell stories, and get people moving. It can also help to improve coordination and balance. Music and dance go hand in hand. Both art forms can create a powerful and emotional experience that brings people together and inspires them. Whether listening to music or dancing, it's a great way to get active and have fun!

One of the biggest trends in Uzbekistani pop culture is the rise of rap and hip-hop music. This genre of music has become increasingly popular among Uzbekistani youth, as it allows them to express their opinions and experiences through their music. In addition, many rap and hip-hop songs have catchy beats and melodies, making them even more popular among the younger generations. Another trend in Uzbekistani pop culture is the increasing popularity of fashion. Many young people are now embracing the latest trends in fashion, which has resulted in a surge in the number of fashion boutiques opening up in major cities throughout the country. Furthermore, many of these boutiques now feature unique designs inspired by Uzbekistani culture and traditions. This has led to a more diverse and eclectic fashion scene in the country, as more people can now express their styles.

Lastly, the popularity of social media has also played an essential role in shaping Uzbekistani pop culture. In the past few years, the number of people using

social media has drastically increased, which has resulted in a surge in the number of people sharing their opinions and experiences online. This has allowed for a greater level of discussion and debate when it comes to popular topics and trends, which has further shaped Uzbekistani pop culture.

In conclusion, pop culture has significantly impacted Uzbekistani society, from influencing fashion and music to shaping social values and economic policies. It has allowed people to express themselves in new ways while providing greater access to international trends. I think that if we learn our knowledge and opportunities from the professional mature masters and teachers of their field and apply it in creative and scientific activities, then Uzbek pop singing will reach the highest heights in the world pop art. I think that through this article, you got some information and opinions about the development of pop art in Uzbekistan.

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